

FIELD EVALUATION OF CERTAIN CHEMICALS AGAINST BORERS OF BHENDI (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L)

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Abstract

Bhendi is an important vegetable crop in India, is heavily infested by a variety of insect pests causing considerable damage and yield reduction. Among the pests, borers are most dreaded pests of national importance. Field experiment was conducted to evaluate the bio efficacy of certain insecticides against borers of bhendi. The treatments imposed were Fenprothrin 30% EC @ 100 g a.i. ha⁻¹, Lambda-Cyhalothrin 5% EC@ 15 g a.i. ha⁻¹, Emamectin benzoate 5 SG @ 11 g a.i. ha⁻¹, Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC@ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹, Quinalphos 25% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha⁻¹, Dimethoate 30% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha⁻¹ and untreated Check. Observations on larval population and fruit damage were made prior to spraying and on 3, 7, 10 and 14 days after spraying from 10 randomly tagged plants per plot and the mean worked out. The fruit damage was assessed based on bore holes found on the fruit. The total number of fruits and infested fruits in ten randomly selected plants per plot were counted and the per cent fruit damage was worked out and the yield of bhendi fruits was also recorded. Results clearly showed that Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC@ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹ followed by emamectin benzoate 5 SG @ 11 g a.i. ha⁻¹ were found to be more effective in controlling bhendi borers in turn yield and better returns. The order of efficacy was Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC@ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹ ≥ emamectin benzoate 5 SG at 11 g a.i. ha⁻¹ > Fenprothrin 30% EC @ 100 g a.i. ha⁻¹ ≥ Lambda-Cyhalothrin 5% EC@ 15 g a.i. ha⁻¹ > Quinalphos 25% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha⁻¹ ≥ Dimethoate 30% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha⁻¹

Key words: Bioefficacy, insecticides, Bhendi, borers**Introduction**

Bhendi (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L) is an important vegetable crop grown for its immature fruits. It is cultivated in tropical, subtropical and mild temperate parts of the world. Bhendi is locally known as Okra and Lady's finger worldwide. It is generally a self-pollinating crop belonging to Malvaceae family. Bhendi is referred as "Queen of Vegetables". The stem of the crop is used in paper industry and also for the extraction of fibre. Bhendi is a good source of vitamin A, B and C also rich in calcium, phosphorus, potassium, protein, carbohydrates, fats, minerals, iron and iodine. Bhendi has quantum of various entities viz., vitamin C (13mg/100g), fat (0.2g/100g), carbohydrate (64mg/100g), iron (1.5mg/100g), moisture (89.6g/100g), protein (1.9g/100g), fibre (1.2g/100g), calories 35 (kcal/100g), and other minerals. The total area and production under bhendi in the world is reported to be 1.26 million ha and 22.29 million tonnes, respectively. India leads the world in bhendi production with an area of 1148 thousand hectares, an annual production of 6346 million tonnes, and a productivity of 11.9 million tonnes/ha, accounting for 5784 thousand tonnes (72% of total global production). The productivity of the crop is low because of insect pest damage at all the stages of crop growth. Among the pests, borers such as *Earias vittella* F and *Earias insulana* Boisduval, causes heavy losses in yield viz., 24.6 to 26.0 percent of shoot and 40 to 100 percent of fruit loss. Chemical insecticides are used as the frontline defense sources against pests, inspite of their drawbacks in India. However, their indiscriminate use has created a number of problems such as pests developing resistance to insecticides, pest resurgence, and bio concentrations of pesticide residues in consumable produce. To overcome the above said problems, identification of new chemical molecules with better insecticidal properties, lower mammalian toxicity and lower application rate with selective action fits very well in the Integrated Pest Management concept. Two such molecules are emamectin benzoate and chlorantraniliprole. Emamectin benzoate belonging to avermectins group has been reported to possess excellent performance against the pests of cotton and vegetables (Sinha *et al.*, 2007; Harish and Patil, 2008, Sharma and Kausik, 2010). It is one of the broad spectrum microbial insecticides derived from the soil actinomycetes *Streptomyces avermitilis*. Chlorantraniliprole is a carboxamide and first anthranilic diamide insecticides, it is a ryanodine receptor activator and is used to protect a wide variety of crops, including corn, cotton, grapes, rice and potatoes. It has a role as a ryanodine receptor agonist. It is an organobromine compound, a member of pyridines, a member of pyrazoles, a pyrazole insecticide, a member of monochlorobenzenes and a secondary carboxamide. With this above background, the present study was taken up to evaluate the

efficacy of certain chemicals especially newer molecules against bhendi borers.

Materials and Methods

Field experiment was conducted at Samuthiram, Manapparai block during 2021-22 to evaluate the bioefficacy of certain chemicals against borers on bhendi. The experiment was carried out in a randomized block design with seven treatments, each replicated three times. The treatments imposed were Fenprothrin 30% EC @ 100 g a.i. ha⁻¹, Lambda-Cyhalothrin 5% EC@ 15 g a.i. ha⁻¹, emamectin benzoate 5 SG @ 11 g a.i. ha⁻¹, Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC@ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹, Quinalphos 25% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha⁻¹, Dimethoate 30% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha⁻¹ and untreated Check. The treatments were imposed two times at 14 days interval commencing from 30th day after sowing with pneumatic Knapsack sprayer using 750 litres of spray fluid per hectare. The observations on larval population and fruit damage were taken prior to spraying and at 3, 7 10 and 14 days after spraying. Larval population was recorded in 10 randomly tagged plants from each plot. The fruit damage was assessed based on bore holes found on the fruit. The total number of fruits and infested fruits in ten randomly selected plants per plot were counted and the per cent fruit damage was worked out and the yield of bhendi fruits were also recorded. The statistical analysis was carried out using IRRISTAT ver 3.1.ANOVA. The data obtained in numbers were transformed to corresponding square root values and percentages were transformed to corresponding angles (arcsine $\sqrt{\text{percentage}}$). The mean values of treatments were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) (Gomez and Gomez, 1976).

Results and discussion

The results of the field experiment showed a significant reduction in the per cent damage caused by borers on bhendi. Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC recorded higher reduction in larval population on 3, 7, 10 and 14 days after treatment, respectively followed by Emamectin benzoate 5 SG and which was on par with each other. In the first spray, Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC @ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹ recorded mean of 2.4 larvae per 10 plants after 3, 7, 10 and 14 days of spray followed by emamectin benzoate 5 SG at 11 g a.i. ha⁻¹ (2.8 No./10 plant). The trend of efficacy of different treatments in the second spray regarding the per cent reduction in larval population was similar to that of first application (Table 1). Regarding fruit damage, Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC @ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹ recorded 12 per cent followed by emamectin benzoate 5 SG at 11 g a.i. ha⁻¹ (14.1%). The fruit yield was significantly higher in all the treatments compared to untreated check (69.26 q ha⁻¹). The highest yield of 92.47q ha⁻¹ was recorded in the plots treated with Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC @ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹ followed by emamectin benzoate 5 SG at 11 g a.i. ha⁻¹ (90.55 q ha⁻¹). Likewise, Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC @ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹ treated plots recorded

highest cost benefit ratio of 1:4.3 followed by emamectin benzoate 5 SG at 11 g a.i.ha⁻¹ (1:4.1) compared to untreated check (1:1.9)(Table 2).The present findings were similar with Kumar *et al.* (2017) and Kushwaha and Painkra (2016) recorded highest yield in Chlorantraniliprole. Devi *et al.* (2014) and Singh *et al.* (2017) observed higher B:C ratio in Emamectin benzoate.

The order of efficacy was Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC@ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹ ≥ emamectin benzoate 5 SG at 11 g a.i.ha⁻¹ > Fenprothrin 30% EC @ 100 g a.i. ha⁻¹ ≥ Lambda-Cyhalothrin 5% EC@15 g a.i. ha⁻¹ > Quinalphos 25% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha⁻¹ ≥ Dimethoate 30% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha⁻¹

Conclusion

Results of the field experiment on bhendi borers revealed that application of Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC@ 25 g a.i. ha⁻¹ followed by emamectin benzoate 5 SG @11 g a.i. ha⁻¹ gave highest mean per cent reduction of borers after two rounds of sprays in turn higher yield and better returns.

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Table 2: Bio Efficacy of insecticides, Yield and Economics (Mean of two sprays)

T.No	Treatments	Fruit Damage (%)					Yield (q/ha)	CB Ratio
		3 DAS	7 DAS	10 DAS	14 DAS	Mean		
T1	Fenprothrin 30% EC @ 100 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	24.3 (29.54)	14.0 (21.98)	12.5 (20.72)	17.6 (24.79)	14.7 (22.49)	86.42	1:3.6
T2	Lambda-Cyhalothrin 5% EC@15 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	23.6 (29.05)	15.2 (22.93)	15.5 (23.14)	18.4 (25.38)	16.4 (23.83)	83.58	1:3.3
T3	Emamectin benzoate 5 SG @ 11 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	24.3 (29.53)	13.7 (21.78)	11.8 (20.12)	16.7 (24.12)	14.1 (22.02)	90.55	1:4.1
T4	Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC@ 25 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	23.6 (29.05)	11.3 (19.62)	10.3 (18.72)	14.3 (22.21)	12.0 (20.19)	92.47	1:4.3
T5	Quinalphos 25% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	24.0 (29.35)	16.9 (24.30)	15.6 (23.31)	19.3 (26.07)	17.3 (24.56)	81.84	1:3.1
T6	Dimethoate 30% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	24.3 (29.53)	18.6 (25.57)	15.9 (23.53)	18.3 (23.34)	17.6 (24.83)	80.62	1:3.0
T7	Untreated Check	23.6 (29.05)	24.1 (29.38)	23.4 (29.56)	25.8 (30.54)	24.8 (29.84)	69.26	1:1.9
	SEm	1.11	0.71	1.43	1.00	0.41	-	-
	CD(p=0.05)	NS	1.54	3.07	2.16	0.89	-	-
	CV (%)	24.65	22.14	28.66	23.58	20.65	-	-

*Figures in parenthesis are arc sin transformed values. DAS : Days After Spray

Table 1: Bio Efficacy of insecticides against bhendi borers

T. No.	Treatments	Larval Population / 10 plants (Nos.)										
		First Spray						Second Spray				
		PTC	3 DAS	7 DAS	10 DAS	14 DAS	Mean	3 DAS	7 DAS	10 DAS	14 DAS	Mean
T1	Fenpropathrin 30% EC @ 100 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	4.7 (2.26)	4.0 (2.10)	2.3 (1.68)	2.3 (1.68)	4.7 (2.26)	3.3 (1.94)	4.0 (2.11)	2.7 (1.77)	2.3 (1.64)	5.7 (2.48)	3.7 (2.02)
T2	Lambda-Cyhalothrin 5% EC@15 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	6.3 (2.59)	6.0 (2.54)	2.3 (1.68)	2.7 (1.77)	2.0 (1.58)	3.3 (1.90)	6.0 (2.54)	3.0 (1.86)	2.0 (1.56)	5.0 (2.34)	4.0 (2.09)
T3	Emamectin benzoate 5 SG @ 11 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	5.0 (2.32)	4.0 (2.10)	2.3 (1.68)	1.7 (1.46)	3.3 (1.94)	2.8 (1.81)	5.7 (2.48)	2.0 (1.56)	1.7 (1.46)	3.7 (2.00)	3.3 (1.89)
T4	Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC@ 25 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	4.3 (2.19)	3.7 (2.03)	1.7 (1.46)	1.3 (1.29)	3.0 (1.86)	2.4 (1.68)	5.0 (2.34)	2.0 (1.58)	1.3 (1.34)	3.0 (1.86)	2.8 (1.79)
T5	Quinalphos 25% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	5.3 (2.41)	5.0 (2.34)	4.0 (2.12)	3.7 (2.04)	5.0 (2.32)	4.4 (2.21)	4.0 (2.11)	4.0 (2.11)	3.7 (2.03)	5.3 (2.41)	4.3 (2.17)
T6	Dimethoate 30% EC@ 200 g a.i. ha ⁻¹	7.0 (2.73)	6.7 (2.67)	5.0 (2.33)	4.3 (2.18)	5.3 (2.40)	5.3 (2.41)	3.0 (1.86)	4.7 (2.26)	4.3 (2.20)	6.3 (2.59)	4.6 (2.24)
T7	Untreated Check	6.7 (2.66)	7.0 (2.72)	9.7 (3.16)	10.3 (3.28)	11.7 (3.46)	10.1 (3.24)	8.0 (2.89)	13.3 (3.71)	13.3 (3.72)	13.7 (3.76)	12.1 (3.53)
	SEm	0.19	0.18	0.16	0.15	0.19	0.15	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.19	0.18
	CD(p=0.05)	NS	0.52	0.46	0.45	0.57	0.41	0.54	0.51	0.51	0.57	0.51
	CV (%)	12.77	12.25	12.48	12.58	14.05	12.55	12.72	13.22	13.98	12.68	14.89

* Figures in parenthesis are square root transformed values. NS – Non-Significant; PTC- Pre-Treatment Count; DAS – Days After Spray